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Detection of the transferable tigecycline resistance gene *tet(X4)* in *Escherichia coli* from pigs in the United Kingdom

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Tigecycline is one of the last-resort critically important antimicrobials and is used to treat MDR bacterial infections.¹ The first report of transferable tigecycline resistance, mediated by newly reported *tet(X3)* and *tet(X4)* genes, in bacterial isolates (including *Escherichia coli*) from livestock occurred in May 2019 from China.² It was suggested that, although tigecycline is not authorized for use in livestock, the extensive use of tetracyclines in livestock could have driven the spread of *tet(X)* variants,³ with subsequent potential for dissemination into human commensal and pathogenic bacterial species.² Both *tet(X3)* and *tet(X4)* confer resistance to all tetracyclines, and can confer high levels of tigecycline resistance (MIC values of 16–32 mg/L),^{2,3} which exceed the EUCAST clinical breakpoint of >0.5 mg/L (<http://www.eucast.org>). Recently, an additional *tet(X)* variant, able to increase the MIC of tetracycline/tigecycline in *E. coli* [*tet(X6)*], was reported.⁴

The Animal and Plant Health Agency (APHA) routinely performs WGS to confirm antimicrobial resistance (AMR) genotypes in *E. coli* isolates obtained from livestock for research or surveillance purposes.^{5,6} Following the report of *tet(X3)* and *tet(X4)* plasmid-mediated tigecycline resistance,² 1988 *E. coli* and *Escherichia fergusonii* genome sequences from livestock and retail meat obtained in the UK between 2013 and 2019 were retrospectively

analysed for the presence of these genes using APHA Seqfinder, which were also confirmed with Abricate.⁵

tet(X4) was detected in one *E. coli* (reference D2.1T5) isolated from a pooled pig faecal sample collected for research purposes from a pig farm in the UK in November 2019. Resistance to tigecycline was confirmed by broth microdilution using the EUSVEC panel,⁷ with D2.1T5 having a tigecycline MIC of 8 mg/L. As expected, the tetracycline MIC was high (>64 mg/L), greater than the EUCAST ECOFF value of 8 mg/L. The isolate also harboured the tetracycline resistance gene *tet(A)*. D2.1T5 displayed clinical resistance to ampicillin (MIC >64 mg/L) and chloramphenicol (MIC >128 mg/L), and harboured the corresponding resistance genes, *bla*_{TEM-1b} and *floR*. It also harboured the streptomycin resistance gene *aadA2* and the lincomycin resistance gene *linG*, although susceptibility to these antimicrobials was not examined. Isolate D2.1T5 is therefore MDR, being resistant to three antimicrobial classes, although it showed susceptibility to the remaining 10 antimicrobials tested.

The serotype of *E. coli* D2.1T5, as inferred by WGS, was O38:H39, and no previously recognized ST could be assigned, although it was closest to ST1140 (single-locus variant with one SNP difference in *purA*). This serotype and ST1140 have been previously reported from livestock.^{8,9} A combined assembly¹⁰ of Illumina NextSeq and Oxford Nanopore MinION sequencing was used to resolve the genomic location of the *tet(X4)*, which was identified on a 129894 bp plasmid (pD2.1T5-*tetX4*, accession number ERS5914483) (Figure 1). The other five AMR genes present in this isolate also resided on this plasmid. The D2.1T5 plasmid appeared to be a hybrid, harbouring both IncX1 and IncY replicon types. Sixty-two percent (~80 kb) of the plasmid had 99.58% nucleotide identity to an Enterobacteria phage (P1 phage-like plasmid) carrying the IncY replicon. An additional ~30 kb region had 98.8% nucleotide identity to IncX1 plasmids harbouring *tet(X4)* reported from *E. coli* isolates in China (accession number MN436006/CP053047/MT197111); this region contained *tet(X4)*, *aadA2*, *floR*, *linG* and *tet(A)*, and was flanked by transposons.

To determine if *tet(X4)*-carrying plasmids similar to D2.1T5 could be detected in Enterobacterales isolates from people in the UK, PHE screened for the presence of *tet(X4)* in short-read WGS data, which were only available from *Escherichia/Shigella* and *Salmonella* isolates obtained from humans between 2014 and 2020 and between 2016 and 2020, respectively. Among 33319 *Escherichia/Shigella* and 58763 *Salmonella* isolates, *tet(X4)* was identified in 4 of 8 *Salmonella* isolates phenotypically resistant to tigecycline and one *Shigella sonnei* isolate. Analysis of the 4.8 kb region harbouring IS6-*rdmC*-*tet(X4)*-IS91 showed that the isolates shared 51%–85% coverage with >99.94% sequence identity; the *Salmonella* reference SRR11230957 had the highest (99.98%) sequence similarity (Figure 1). However, outside of this region, the AMR gene content of the sequences was different, e.g. the *Salmonella* harboured *cmlA1* instead of *floR*, and *sul2* and *dfrA12*, which were not identified in pD2.1T5-*tetX4*. The remaining

Figure 1. Comparative analysis of *tet(X4)*-harbouring *E. coli* plasmid (pD2.1T5-*tetX4*; black inner ring, accession number ERS5914483) with other published *tet(X4)*- and *tet(X6)*-carrying plasmids and chromosomes from China, *Salmonella* and *Shigella* isolates from PHE collection and plasmids/Enterobacteria phage with high sequence identity to ~80 kb, using the BLAST Ring Image Generator. Each concentric ring displays the nucleotide similarity between pD2.1T5-*tetX4* and the other sequences in the outer rings. The shade of colour indicates the BLAST percentage identity. The *tet(X6)* plasmids and chromosomes are grouped together. The outermost ring shows the annotation of pD2.1T5-*tetX4*. The *tet(X4)* gene is highlighted green, other AMR genes are highlighted pink and the plasmid replicon sequences are in grey. This figure appears in colour in the online version of JAC and in black and white in the print version of JAC.

Salmonella from humans also harboured differing proportions of the pD2.1T5-*tetX4*, as did a number of *E. coli* and *E. fergusonii* reported in other studies (Figure 1).

Notably, only one isolate of a large collection of Enterobacteriaceae isolates carried *tet(X4)*, suggesting a very low prevalence of this resistance. The genetic differences observed in the plasmids harbouring *tet(X4)* in the available human and animal isolates from the UK are not suggestive of direct or recent epidemiological links between the human and animal sectors within the UK. The genetic similarity between the UK isolate and isolates reported from China, of the region of the plasmid bearing the *tet(X4)* gene, including the juxtaposition of the *floR* gene, is notable; the findings indicating potential international dissemination of this structure. Surveillance for mobile tetracycline resistance should be maintained, in particular to survey the risk of the emergence of clones resistant to tetracycline and other critically important antimicrobials.

The sequence data for this study are deposited at the European Nucleotide Archive under the accession number PRJEB43587.

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Transparency declarations

None to declare.

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